

Ethics, Islam and leadership in this time of COVID 19

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In the name of God, the Beneficent, the Merciful, and (with) prayers and blessings on Muhammad and his family.

All praise is for Allah, who rescued us from the darkness of ignorance through the illumination of knowledge, and through it He granted us the discernment to avoid falling into erroneous deception. He laid down for us in the Shariah of Muhammad a lofty standard and a manifest guide. This was the best of His abundant blessings that He showered on us and the best of His venerable gifts that He bestowed on us.

The obligations imposed by the Shariah, by ijma, are not merely for bringing people under the authority of the Deen, but for the affirmation of the purposes of the Lawgiver in securing their interests both of the Deen and of this world. Each rule of the Shariah expresses: the preservation of one of the necessities such as Deen, life, reasoning faculty, progeny and wealth. These are the foundations of civilisation preserved by each community, without which all interests of this world would be lost along with salvation in the Hereafter. The Shariah is that path to the watering hole. The path of guidance and the path of being and living correct. It is intrinsically bound in enjoining ethical and moral behaviour.

وَتَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْبِرِّ وَالْقَوَىٰ ۖ وَلَا تَعَاوَنُوا عَلَى الْإِثْمِ وَالْعُدْوَانِ ۗ وَاتَّقُوا اللَّهَ ۖ إِنَّ اللَّهَ شَدِيدُ الْعِقَابِ

And help one another in goodness and piety, and do not help one another in sin and aggression; and be careful of (your duty to) Allah; surely Allah is severe in punishment.
(Sūratul Mā'idah, No. 5, Āyat 2)

In order to create a framework of calling to goodness and refraining from what can be considered bad actions, human beings realise the need to have regulatory systems, called laws. Law may be a system of rules and guidelines which are enforced through social institutions to control behaviour. Laws are nowadays understood to be made by governments, specifically by their legislatures. In Islam we understand that Allah is the ultimate Lawgiver, and His Messenger played a pivotal role in giving us the case studies for application of the Quranic injunctions. The formation of laws themselves could also be influenced by a constitution and the rights encoded therein. For Muslims, this constitution, remains the Quran, and nothing can take its equal or place. The law, and how it is interpreted shapes politics, economics and society in countless ways and serves as a social mediator of relations between people. It becomes the criterion by which an ethical society is established.

Hanafy and Sallam (1988) classified ethical principles of Islam into six categories:

Sidq (Truthfulness), Amanah (Trust), Ihlas (Sincerity), Ikhwa (Brotherhood), Ilm (Knowledge and science), Adl (justice). These principles were the foundation of sound transaction and social life of an ethical and moral civilization. Much of this has to do with individual behaviour. Individual effort and seeking the good and helping others to it was essential. Individual behaviour in turn was influenced by factors such as indicated in the diagram below, namely stages of moral development, personal values, family influence, peer influence, life experience and situational factors:

Figure 1: Factors influencing an individual

Cooperating with other believers in goodness has been highly emphasized in Islam. Business practice and transacting with one another ethically is primal in the rules of Shariah, know as Mu’amamat. When believers work together there’s motivation, enthusiasm and an increase in spirit. This can however only be done when the individual takes stock of his life and what lead him to that point of realization. Hence the emphasis in Islam on Tazkia-tu-nafs. The lower or animal self is not cognisant of the self and only in its needs and wants. It is the material self. The conscientious self is a higher developed stage. Where the need and awareness of others, their needs and their concerns become attributable in one’s own space. This is where societal awareness comes in.

The stages of moral development have been outlined by Piaget and Kohler in their treatises on the subject, which deals with the pre-conventional stage, normally children below 7, all the way to stages in adulthood. The affect family and peer values have on the formation of personal values is directly attributable, but also balanced against life experiences and situational factors. Hence a family that pays scant or little regard to the Shariah, will not give rise to a law confirming society, but a rebellious one.

Individual ethics can then be seen to be comprised of the following three components as shown below :

Figure 2 : Factors influencing individual ethics

Legal interpretations that is not having a sense of “Godliness”, seeking the pleasure of Allah in it, will automatically lead to ethically incorrect interpretations. Individual ethics is also very heavily influenced by these Individual Factors.

Ho and Wang, (2012), alluded that ethics can generally be defined as the principles of morally acceptable conduct of individuals and that cultural background can have an influence in individualism . Researchers state here that individualistic cultures attach more importance to personal matters and self interest. In such communities the links between individuals are loose, and groups membership is flexible. Individuals who are high on individualism tend to value personal time, freedom, and independence. Such individuals tend to place personal interests above group interests.

So what then makes a person to be ethical and unethical? The factors that outline ethical behaviours are diverse, but all factors unite when a individual makes a final judgement on the way to act. The Shariah affect how law as it is currently applied in the dominant Western culture, is interpreted. For instance in our legal Interpretations we do not accept Caveat Emptor of Western Law, which gives privilege. Rather we obey the Messenger of Allah who advised:

On the authority of Ibn Umar, who said that the Messenger of Allah (saw) said: "Do not sell fruits until they have ripened." And he forbade (both) the seller and the purchaser (to engage in such a transaction).

Ibn Majah, Hadith No: 2214

Allahs Mesenger forbade the sale of fruits till they are almost ripe. Anas was asked, what is meant by “ they are almost ripe”. He replied, “ Till they become red.”. He said further : “ If Allah spoiled the fruits, what right would one have to take the money of one’s brother. (ie, other people)”?

Sahih Bukhari 3.403

While family don’t always dictate morality, they are usually the first to express and indicate the ethical boundaries in the eyes of children. Usually parents consider it one of their essential tasks to instil an awareness of right and wrong in their children. Furthermore young minds absorb the actions of their family, which in turn impinge on the morality of the child. The ethical standards of young people are a direct consequence in many cases of the their parents’ or members of their family’s practices.

The Prophet (s.a.w.) emphasized the importance of family nurturing when he said:-

“Command your children to pray when they become seven years old, and discipline them for it prayer) when they become ten years old; and arrange their beds (to sleep) separately.”

Organizational aspects can also influence individual behaviour, ie organization involved in selling wine or having to sign documents allowing the sale of it. Thus Islamic ethics is in direct conflict with codes of practice and cultures which allow this. In a study by Wartick and Cochran the principles of social responsibility was highlighted in the transactional environment. This hoghlights the shift from the individual to the social, hence individual ethics giving rise to the effect in society.

More importantly, we know that trading is the most common reason for people to interact with each other. The principles of social responsibility accept the existence and importance of both economic and social responsibility of companies. Economic responsibility is a component of social responsibility, which in turn depends on individual ethics. Another factor is social responsiveness . Social responsibility and social responsiveness are in fact complementary. It is this which together

provide the means to achieving corporate social obligations. Hence positive trading and business practices which allows for growth in society apart from the Capitalist project of self centred wealth amassing of individuals.

There is a need for companies to identify and address social issues, develop processes of response and assess the outcomes. This is a drive towards sound and ethical business practice. This is the basis of having and keeping the transactions conform to the Shariah.

The Prophet was saying something in a gathering while a Bedouin came to ask him, “ When would the Hour take Place?” The Messenger of Allah continued his talk, so some people said that the Messenger heard the question but did not like what the Bedouin asked. The Messenger finished his speech and said: “Where is the questioner who asked about the Hour?” The Bedouin replied: “I am here Apostle of Allah.” Then the Messenger of Allah said: “When honesty is lost, then wait for the Hour.” The Bedouin asked : “ how will honesty be lost?”, to which the Messenger replied :

“When power and authority come in the hands of unfit persons, then wait for the Hour.”

Sahih Bukhari 1:56

Now, a society that has become trapped in the modern capitalist economy of spiralling debt, from individual liability to corporate and national debt, will have the most conniving and ruthless specimens rise to the top of its leadership roles.

Somebody said to the Messenger of Allah: “Why do you so frequently seek refuge in Allah from being in debt”. He replied : “A person in debt lies when he speaks and break promises when he makes them”

Sahih Bukhari 1.795

It is thus well known that laws not founded on a set of ethical principles will rarely succeed in reaching their objectives. The reason why ethics is required as a foundation is that the law, in itself, is insufficient to cause people to do the “right” thing. The law does not provide an incentive for people to do the right thing—it simply provides a disincentive to not do the wrong thing. This is why a society that is Law Abiding rarely become a civilization of goodness, but instead a civilization of deceit and treachery.

For most people that punishment is not sufficient to keep them from doing wrong things. Many a time we see that citizens weigh up the risk of being caught and sometimes doing the legally wrong thing is perceived as sufficiently low risk. Hence an escalation in criminal activity.

Modern society is replete with contradictions. Thus in some situations, the fact that something is ethical does not necessarily make it legal. Today, laws are created as the result of an ethical breach identified by society. And thus the relativism of ethics can have an important role in how things are seen, and how people may respond to a breach. For example the matter of polygamy. Modern society decided to abandon it. To practice bigamy or polygamy would therefore be regarded as unethical. To formally indicate society’s dissatisfaction with this unethical behaviour, a law is created that specifically defines polygamy as inappropriate and prescribes a penalty associated with the failure to comply with the law. In this way, ethics contributes to the formation of law.

Hence if we determine that ethics is about doing what is right and that it is a determiner of what is right and what is wrong, then what of Allah? While we certainly recognise that both ethics and morality has something to do with what’s “right” and “wrong”, we also need to understand the differences here. For instance, an individual’s own principles about something right or wrong is called a moral. On the other hand, following a series of rules that is provided to an individual such as

the law is referring as ethics. Ethics and materialism leads to a different set of principles in business transactions as well as in leadership. Ethics based on Shariah , which is putting Allah as the Lawgiver, gives rise to an entirely different civilization matrix.

So enter a Virus. And the world gone mad and in need of ethical leadership. Here it is well for us to note what some definitions of leadership have been defined as by others. For instance Hollander says leadership is :

"The process whereby one individual influences other group members toward the attainment of defined group or organizational goals." [Holander, 1985]

Deming, the renowned leadership guru said:

"A good leader is one that makes many leaders, listens to people and forgives a mistake".

Moreover the Majestic Quran defines leadership as based on skill and trustworthiness. Both is a requirement.

One of the women said, "O my father, hire him. Indeed, the best one you can hire is the strong and the trustworthy."

Surah al-Qasas 28:26

Yusuf said, "Appoint me over the treasury of the land. Indeed, I am trusty and knowledgeable."

Surah Yusuf 12:55

And finally, to conclude this point, we look at the report from Tabbarani, that the Noblest of mankind, the Messenger of Allah said:

"The leader of the people is their servant."

Conclusion:

Stillwell (2020) says emphatically that these are unprecedented times. He relates this time as life altering and worse than the Great Depression and World War II and sees it as having paradigm-shifting impact.

The time upon us is chaotic. It is a world in apparent turmoil. A time when social media is rampant and out of control. When established media is vague and embedded. When business practice is capitalistic and opportunistic. When political leadership is seen as arrogant and insensitive. When the medical profession is seen as brave soldiers or mop-up squads. When police become enforcers, and when the public resort to fear and rebellion. We are daily confronted with ethical dilemmas and in making decision we should now more than ever before fall back to being people who confirm law. Some would say that the secular law, as it stands is a donkey. It is for us to aid it along and make it work in the interest of the poor and downtrodden. To give life to its spirit, not just its letter, and to bring Allah back to how we understand law. As Muslims we should look deeply at what the Shariah

requires from us , in all matters and circumstances. It is a time to be firmly grounded in what Allah wants from us and to look for guidance from the example of the Messenger of Allah. It is a time to serve and protect the greater good. Wama taufeeq illa billah.

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